

Effect of Compaction on the Kinetics of Thermal Dehydroxylation of Fire Clay

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Kinetics of thermal dehydroxylation of fire clay which is mainly disordered kaolinite, have been studied as a function of compaction of the loose aggregates. Kinetic parameters have been correlated with the pressure of pelletisation and also the disorderness inherent in the crystal structure.

Structurally fire clay is disordered kaolinite¹. Various workers studied kinetics of kaolinite. Shlykov and Shorniktrudov² studied the kinetics of dehydration of clay at 600–900°. Murray and White³ showed that the isothermal decomposition of clay mineral proceeds according to the first-order kinetics. Holt *et al.*⁴ found that at pressure near 1 mm/Hg, the dehydration of kaolinite is diffusion-controlled. Criado *et al.*⁵ studied the kaolinite dehydroxylation and explained why different investigators ascribed both first order kinetics and diffusion mechanism to this reaction. Stock⁶ studied the significance of structural factors in dehydroxylation of kaolinite.

The present investigations was undertaken to study the effect of compaction of fire clay on the kinetics of thermal decomposition. For all commercial purposes fire clay are used in compact form specially where firing is considered. The basis for understanding the rate processes was the Arrhenius relationship which states that the logarithm of the reaction rate constant (K) is proportional to the reciprocal of the absolute temperature. The isothermal experiments were conducted under identical condition. The work was concentrated to the dehydroxylation zone. The importance of this study is that depending upon the rate of reaction and the activation energy, heat utilisation in commercial can be economised.

Results and Discussion

The silica-alumina ratio of the samples are higher

than ordinary kaolinite (Table 1) which might be due to the presence of free silica or superimposed silica layers. All the ferric oxide present in the sample could not be removed completely by chemical treatment and this retention might be correlated to the disorderness of the crystals.

TABLE 1—PHYSICOCHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE PURIFIED RAJHARA FIRE CLAY

Constituents	Composition (%)
SiO ₂	59.44
Al ₂ O ₃	26.88
Fe ₂ O ₃	1.43
Loss on ignition	10.25
Cation-exchange capacity	8.6 meq/100 g
DTA peak temp (°C)	561 (endothermic)
	985 (exothermic)

The dehydroxylation peak temperature in the DTA curve of the sample was slightly lower than that of pure kaolinite which was due to the presence of disorderness in the experimental sample compared to pure kaolinite.

The study on the kinetics on dehydroxylation of the sample was carried out in order to have an idea about the mechanism of the dehydroxylation process as well as the rate-determining step. The sample was taken both in the powder and the pellet form. The plot of weight-loss against time (Fig. 1) revealed exponential behaviour which suggested the application of first order kinetics.

Fig. 1. Weight-loss vs time plots of the fire clay pellets formed at 1350 kg cm^{-2} pressure.

Applying Guggenheim's kinetic equation,

$$\log \Delta L = (-K_1 t / 2.303) + \log L_\alpha (1 - \exp(-K_1 \Delta t))$$

the reaction rate constants (K_1) and the equilibrium weight-losses (L_α) were calculated (Table 2). K_1 and L_α values were calculated from the $\log \Delta L$ vs time linear plots at different temperatures (plots not shown). Here, ΔL is the difference between the weight-loss at time $(t + \Delta t)$ and at time t , the time interval Δt between the two sets of readings being kept fixed at values greater than twice the time for 50% dehydration. The reaction rate constants decreased with the increase in pressure. Some

anomalies were observed which were due to anisometric nature of the particles and their orientation. Moreover, at higher pressure, there was possibility of disintegration of coarser grains. The powder had higher reaction rate constants than the pellets at all the temperatures which was due to the higher surface area of the powder compared to the pellets. The variation in equilibrium weight-loss values with pressure was always within a narrow range. This was quite expected as any variation in compaction might alter the rate of dehydration but not the final loss at definite time. No positive correlation could be achieved between the applied pressure of pelletisation and reaction rate constants or

equilibrium weight-loss which might be due to heterogeneity in particle size and also their orientation.

TABLE 2—REACTION RATE CONSTANT (K_1) AND EQUILIBRIUM WEIGHT LOSS (L_∞) VALUES AS CALCULATED FROM LOG ΔL VS TIME PLOTS OF FIRE CLAY POWDER AND PELLETS FORMED AT DIFFERENT PRESSURES

Temp. °C	Pellet-forming pressure kg cm ⁻²	K_1 min ⁻¹	L_∞ g
500	Powder	0.11	0.03
	1 150	0.04	0.03
	1 350	0.04	0.03
	1 550	0.04	0.03
530	Powder	0.22	0.04
	1 150	0.09	0.03
	1 350	0.08	0.03
	1 550	0.08	0.03
560	Powder	0.34	0.04
	1 150	0.17	0.03
	1 350	0.13	0.03
	1 550	0.13	0.03
590	Powder	0.46	0.04
	1 150	0.28	0.03
	1 350	0.21	0.04
	1 550	0.20	0.04
620	Powder	0.68	0.05
	1 150	0.44	0.04
	1 350	0.41	0.05
	1 550	0.40	0.05
650	Powder	1.00	0.05
	1 150	0.65	0.06
	1 350	0.67	0.06
	1 550	0.73	0.06

Extent of validity of the first order kinetics (as determined from the log $(L_\infty - L)/L_\infty$ vs time plots; figure not shown) was a direct function of temperature but was more or less independent of pressure (Table 3). This appeared to be due to fact that with increase in pressure heat conductivity increased which nullified the effect of back-pressure created due to the compaction.

TABLE 3—EXTENT OF VALIDITY OF FIRST ORDER LAW

Temp.	Percent validity of first order law of pellets at different forming pressure (kg cm ⁻²)			
	Powder	1150	1350	1550
500	38.34	37.13	37.63	37.63
530	43.11	43.77	43.10	42.46
560	45.05	44.41	45.67	45.70
590	50.75	49.30	50.45	49.89
620	56.35	56.85	55.84	55.80
650	59.26	58.79	57.93	58.79

In dehydroxylation, water formed from structural hydroxyl groups was lost by diffusion giving an unstable network of silica and alumina. The last trace of water was removed at a different rate from the prevailing at the earlier stage as reflected through the flattening of the rate curves. This deviation might be due to the fact that during the early stage of reaction, recombination process due to cooling effect might interface with the course of reaction. The rate constants at the final stage of dehydration (K_2) were calculated (Table 4) from the relation,

$$K_2 = \frac{(dL/dt)}{(L_\infty - L)}$$

where dL/dt is the slope of weight-loss vs time curves at the point of dehydration beyond which the first order kinetics were not followed. The K_2 values were always lower than the corresponding K_1 values and the texture of the compacts had very little effect on this.

TABLE 4—VALUE OF REACTION RATE CONSTANTS (K_2) OF FIRE CLAY POWDER AND PELLETS FORMED AT DIFFERENT FORMING PRESSURES

Temp.	K_2 (min ⁻¹) for different forming pressure (kg cm ⁻²)			
	Powder	1150	1350	1550
500	0.05	0.03	0.04	0.02
530	0.09	0.13	0.10	0.08
560	0.22	0.16	0.16	0.15
590	0.32	0.27	0.24	0.15
620	0.33	0.36	0.20	0.26
650	0.50	0.31	0.18	0.18

The activation energies both at the initial and the final stages were calculated using Arrhenius equation,

$$\log K = \log (Pz) - E/4.578T$$

E_1 (initial stage) and E_2 (final stage) values were calculated from the Arrhenius linear plots (not shown). In each cases E_2 values (initial stage) were higher than E_1 values (final stage) (Table 5). This clearly indicated that the reaction is dependent on the concentration of the reacting species. Upto 1350 kg cm⁻² pressure, both E_1 and E_2 followed a direct relationship with pressure, i.e. it increased but at

the highest pressure, it decreased. The increase in activation energy appeared to be due to the back-pressure created within the compacts. But at very high pressure, upon compaction the effect of back-pressure had been eliminated due to the increase in conductivity. Moreover, at very high pressure, there was possibility of breakage of individual particles thereby creating flaws within the compacts which helped in rapid diffusion of the escaping water molecules.

TABLE 5—ACTIVATION ENERGIES FROM ARRHENIUS PLOT OF FIRE CLAY POWDER AND PELLETS FORMED AT DIFFERENT PRESSURES DURING DEHYDROXYLATION

Forming pressure (kg cm ⁻²)	Activation energy (kcal mol ⁻¹)		
	<i>E</i> ₁	<i>E</i> ₂	<i>E</i> ₂ / <i>E</i> ₁
Powder	18.59	21.45	1.10
1 150	25.11	28.80	1.15
1 350	26.14	30.64	1.17
1 550	22.38	28.38	1.26

The ratio of *E*₂/*E*₁ was always higher than one and upto 1350 kg cm⁻² pressure there was no great difference in the ratio. This was found to be related to the uniform texture of the material during dehydroxylation.

Conclusion : (i) The reaction rate constants at the initial stage of dehydration of the pellets were lower than the powder which clearly indicated that compaction produced greater resistance to the diffusion of formed water molecules from the interior to the surface. With the increase in pressure, the values of the reaction rate constants decreased. (ii)

The reaction rate constants at the later stage of dehydration was also decreased with the increase in the pressure of compaction which is another indication of the effect of compaction of the rate of dehydration. (iii) Activation energies both at the initial and final stages increased with the increase in pressure upto 1350 kg cm⁻², but then at the highest pressure, it decreased. This might be due to combination of various effects, such as, back-pressure, flaws in the texture, heat conductivity, etc.

Experimental

Rajhara fire clay of Indian origin was selected for the present investigation. The clay was purified from its associated impurities. The sample was chemically analysed. Differential thermal analysis of the sample was carried out with a Shimadzu DT-40 thermal analyser at a heating rate of 10^o/min. Kinetic study of thermal dehydroxylation of the sample in the pellet form was performed with a thermobalance.

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